

FUMA GENE2FUNC outputs for all the mapped genes

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1 Gene Expression Heatmap

Average expression per label (log2 transformed). Order genes by cluster. Order tissues by cluster.

1.2 GTEx v8 30 general tissue types

2 Tissue specificity, Differentially expressed genes

Significantly enriched DEG sets ($P_{bon} < 0.05$) are highlighted in red. Order tissue by up-regulated DEG P values.

2.1 GTEx v8 54 tissue types

2.2 GTEx v8 30 general tissue types

Significantly enriched DEG sets ($P_{bon} < 0.05$) are highlighted in red. Order tissue by up-regulated DEG P values.

3 Enrichment of input genes in Gene Sets

3.1 BioCarta (MsigDB c2)(1)

3.2 Cancer gene neighborhoods (MsigDB c4)(5)

3.3 Cancer gene modules (MsigDB c4)(32)

3.4 All Canonical Pathways (MsigDB c2)(15)

3.5 Chemical and Genetic perturbation gene sets (MsigDB c2)(171)

3.6 All computational gene sets (MsigDB c4)(35)

3.7 Curated gene sets(158)

3.8 GO biological processes (MsigDB c5)(54)

3.9 GO cellular components (MsigDB c5)(32)

3.10 GO molecular functions (MsigDB c5)(51)

3.11 GWAS catalog reported genes(100)

3.12 Hallmark gene sets (MsigDB h)(5)

3.15 Oncogenic signatures (MsigDB c6)(7)

3.16 Positional gene sets (MsigDB c1)(15)

3.17 Reactome (MsigDB c2)(6)

3.18 TF targets (MsigDB c3)(38)

3.19 WikiPathways(3)

